

vocabularies are better to teach (Pishghadam & Shayesteh, 2017), and how to teach them effectively. Consistent with this argument, Widdowson (1978) contended that the criteria for vocabulary teaching are frequency and prototype. Driven by the same concern, cultural factors (Gairns & Redman, 1989), and learnability (McCarthy, 1990) are among the elements referred to as criteria for vocabulary teaching (Pishghadam & Shayesteh, 2017). This underpins the fact that all of the techniques and approaches for vocabulary teaching should be well-balanced in a way that provides an appropriate situation for incidental and deliberate word learning (Baleghizadeh, 2016).

Some vocabularies may be absorbed much easier and quicker, caused by a higher level of emotioncy. The term emotioncy refers to an amalgam of emotion and frequency of the exposure to various senses (Pishghadam et al., 2016). As Pishghadam and Shayesteh (2016) put it, individuals experience different emotions in confronting a novel concept. This experience is much more highlighted in learning a second/foreign language, because L1 emotions are carried into the L2/Ln learning context by students. Furthermore, Shahian et al. (2017) claim that learning a new word is difficult when a word conveys little or no emotion. EBLI is based on emotionalism (Pishghadam, Adamson et al., 2013); in emotionalisation, the crucial role of prior emotion is emphasized.

Emotion-Based Language Instruction (EBLI) as a novel approach to the second language (L2) acquisition assumes that various language entities (e.g., vocabularies) cause a different degree of emotion; the stronger this emotion is the faster and deeper learners can learn (Pishghadam et al., 2013). EBLI focuses on emotional competency in learners. That is, prior emotion is highlighted in EBLI. According to Pishghadam, Adamson, et al. (2013) the input should be based on vocabularies with which the students have an already-established emotional relationship. These vocabularies should be a little beyond their levels of emotioncy.

Words as the basis of language formation are not neutral; they convey different emotions. For instance, in first language acquisition words like "mommy" and "daddy" are learned quickly not just due to their high frequencies but also via the emotions (love, peace, happiness, hope, etc.) that are conveyed with these terms (Greenspan & Shanker, 2004). Moreover, emotional experiences can be applied to semantics as well as syntax. The word, "more" for instance, reminds children of quantity and something tasty (Shanker & Greenspan, 2005). Considering first language acquisition, children attempt to use a word referring to the unknown world while in second/foreign language learning context—just the opposite occurs (Pishghadam et al., 2017). To be more specific, in L2 learning context children lack

suitable words referring to the world information transferred from L1 experiences (Greenspan, 2001). In this situation, learners make use of their previous experiences to learn new materials (Son & Goldstone, 2009). That means they link the vocabularies of the first and the second language; the more the level of their emotioncy (emotion + frequency) is, the more natural and comfortable they can learn (Pishghadam et al., 2016). In this regard, Pishghadam, Adamson, et al. (2013) introduce three pivot constituents to the related literature.

In the era of technology, learning a new language is an indispensable component of each person's life. Mostly, second/foreign language learning happens in academic settings such as schools and language institutes. Classrooms as the center of the academic world are emotional places (Pekrun, 2014) influencing learners' performance, identity development, motivation, and success (Schutz & Pekrun, 2007). The advances in the humanistic approaches (Mendez Lopez and Pea Aguilar, 2013) provide a new horizon in the realm of education and, in turn, leading to significant attention to emotional states and affective factors. This is due to the fact that, emotions are among the most influential factors in the development and effectiveness of teaching and learning. Teachers, as the center of educational systems, are like a bridge between knowledge and the learners (Heydarnejad, Hosseini Fatemi, & Ghonsooli, 2017). While teaching, they are exposed to various pleasant and unpleasant emotions. Effective teachers are those who are capable of regulating their emotions; they are mostly motivated teachers. Motivation immunizes language teachers productively which in turn enhances their effectiveness and promotes their students' achievement.

Conclusion: Speaking and writing are called productive skills because learners are responsible for producing language themselves (Harmer, 2007). Capability in these skills is due to many factors such as knowledge of vocabulary, grammar, discourse, culture, as well as sociolinguistics (Chastain, 1998). Speaking is supposed to be the product of choosing suitable vocabulary and grammatical structure to express the intended meaning. Writing, the next productive skill depends on many factors. This challenging language skill requires linguistic knowledge, grammar, vocabulary, and thinking strategies (Yavuz-Erkan and Iflazoglu-Saban, 2011). In the same vein, Hidayati (2018) refers to external and internal challenges in teaching English writing skill. The external challenges can be teaching facilities, the class condition and time while the internal ones include motivation, reading habits of the students, native language interference, and linguistic competence. In addition, McLeod (1987) described writing as an emotional and cognitive activity. Since "No one is a 'native speaker' of writing"

(Leki, 1992, p. 10), writing is to be assumed as an intimidating task both for native as well as for non-natives, in particular EFL learners (Cheung, 2016).

Teaching emotive language entails selecting words that stir the emotions of the students. Moreover, it requires encouraging the learners to think aloud and be creative. The success of teaching emotive language lies in the ability to select words that are not only easy to understand but also trigger the imagination. The primary objective of using emotive language is to draw the attention of the students. A teacher has to use words with favorable connotation to avoid misunderstandings.

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